

Current status

Ideally, all are now at the end of the modelling component of Phase 1. Currently, 23% of participants have completed all stages (Table 1). Please endeavour to complete all stages as soon as possible.

Table 1: Current status of each modelling group

- 3.5: Stage 3.5 back?
- 4d: Stage 4 data released?
- 4: Stage 4 output & parameters returned?
- VL92 re-run: ✓/✗ will/will not re-run; - await response
- MC – model classification ✓confirmed; - await response
- TBC – to be confirmed

Model number	3.5	4d	4	4, Optimised for:	VL92 re-run?	MC
a) Stages 1 – 2 complete						
11					✗	✓
12	✓	✓			✗	✓
13	✓				✗	✓
14	✓	✓			✗	✓
16	✓	✓	✓	[Q*], [Q _H], [Q*,Q _H ,Q _E]	✓	✓
17					-	-
21	✓	✓			✗	✓
22					-	-
25	✓	✓	✓	[Q*,Q _H ,Q _E]	✗	✓
28					✗	✓
30	✓	✓			✗	-
31		✓	✓	[Q*], [Q _H], [Q _E],[Q _H ,Q _E],[Q*,Q _H]	✓	✓
32		✓	✓	[Q*,Q _H ,Q _E]	✗	✓
33		✓	✓	[Q*,Q _H ,Q _E]	✗	✓
35	✓	✓			✓	✓
36	✓	✓	✓	[Q*,Q _H ,Q _E]	✓	✓
37	✓	✓			✗	✓
39					✓	✓
42	✓	✓			✓	✓
43	✓	✓			✓	✓
46		✓			✓	✓
47					✓	-
49	✓	✓			✗	✓
50		✓			✗	-
b) Await stages 1 – 2						
26					✓	-
41					-	-

AMS Annual Meeting, Phoenix

There is a session on Wednesday morning of the conference (14 January) with some papers concerned with the intercomparison. It would be great if we could meet as a group (Wednesday Lunchtime?). Please let us know if you are planning to attend so that we can organise a time.

7th International Conference on Urban Climate

The following abstract has been submitted for the IAUC meeting in Japan next year. We encourage others to submit papers related to this comparison. Please let us know if you plan to attend.

7th International Conference on Urban Climate

Location: Yokohama, Japan.
When: 29 June – 3 July 2009
Abstract deadline: 15 December 2008

Grimmond CSB, Blackett M and Best M with Baik J, Bohnenstengel S, Calmet I, Chen F, Dandou A, Fortuniak K, Gouvea M, Hamdi R, Hendry M, Kondo H, Krayenhoff S, Lee S, Loridan T, Martilli A, Masson V, Miao S, Oleson K, Pigeon G, Porson A, Salamanca F, Shashua-Bar L, Steeveheld G, Trombou M, Voogt J, Zhang N

Results from the international urban surface energy balance model comparison study

There are now a number of urban models within the community, which vary in complexity from simple schemes to the detailed representation of momentum and energy fluxes, even distributed within the atmospheric boundary layer. In addition to variations in complexity, these models also differ in parameter requirements and on a more practical level, the cost of running the models. Whilst many of these models have been evaluated against observational datasets, with some models even using the same observations, these have not been done in a controlled way that enables comparisons to be made between the models. Such controlled comparisons, however, have been shown in the past to provide scientific insight into both the mechanics of the models and also the physics of the real world, for instance the PILPS experiments. This presentation will describe the progress that has been made so far with regards to the urban model comparison project.

Parameter Types and Values

Many parameters have different names but are essentially the same or can be reformulated. From six 'fundamental' parameters (Table 2 a, b), many urban morphology parameters (~16) can be derived (Table 2 c-d). Overall there are 219 parameters (Table 3) used by 26 models.

Table 2: Urban morphology parameters.

Parameter Alternative name	Symbol	Derivation	Units	Models which use parameter
<i>(a) 'Fundamental'</i>				
Mean roof level	z_H		m	Most
Mean building width	L_X		m	16, 17, 22, 35, 42
• Mean building length • Mean block length	L_Y	$L_Y = L_X S_{LY}$ $S_{LY} = L_Y / L_X$ – relative length factor	m	12, 14, 16
• Mean canyon width • Mean building separation	W_X	$W_Y = W_X S_{WY}$ $S_{WY} = W_Y / W_X$ – relative length factor	m	11, 12, 13, 14, 16, 21, 28, 30, 32, 35, 37, 42, 43, 49
• Canyon length • Mean block length	W_Y	$W_Y = W_X S_{WY}$	m	12, 14, 16
<i>(b) Definition required but not used</i>				
Area	A_T	$A_T = [L_X + W_X][L_Y + W_Y]$	m ²	
<i>(c) Commonly Used (can be derived from above)</i>				
Canyon height to width ratio	λ_s	$\lambda_s = \frac{z_H}{W_X}$	N/A	11, 12, 13, 14, 16, 21, 25, 28, 30, 31, 32, 35, 37, 42, 43, 46, 49
• Plan area ratio • Building area factor • Roof area ratio • Building coverage ratio • Building fraction	λ_p	$\lambda_p = \frac{L_X L_Y}{A_T}$	N/A	11, 12, 13, 14, 16, 17, 21, 22, 25, 49, 28, 30, 31, 32, 33, 35, 36, 37, 39, 41, 42, 43, 46, 47, 50
Road area fraction	λ_{road}	$\lambda_{road} = \frac{W_X W_Y}{A_T}$	N/A	16, 25, 31, 35, 36, 42
Frontal area index	λ_F	$\lambda_F = \frac{z_H L_Y + z_H L_X}{A_T}$	N/A	35, 42

Table 3: All parameters, ordered by the number of models (#) which use them and colour coded into the following classes (C):

F	Fraction of cover
E	Emissivity
A	Albedo
M	Material related (not albedo/emissivity)
T	Temperature (initial state, fixed)
U	Urban
V	Vegetation
S	Soil
QF	Anthropogenic heat flux

Many of these may be referring to the same thing. **Please identify what YOU consider to be the same so we can reduce the duplication.** For each class eventually we would like to have a similar table as we created for the morphology (Table 2).

C	Parameter	#
M	Emissivity of roof	20
F	Buildings fraction	20
M	Albedo of roof	20
M	Volumetric heat capacity of roof layer	20
U	Material roughness length above, for momentum – roof	18
M	Emissivity of impervious road	18
M	Albedo of impervious road	18
M	Volumetric heat capacity of impervious road	18
M	Number of roof layers	18
U	Roof level (building height)	17
M	Wall layer volumetric heat capacity	17
M	Thermal conductivity of roof layer	17
U	Roughness length above canyon for momentum	16
M	Number of Wall layers	16
M	Wall layer thermal conductivity	16
M	Thermal conductivity of impervious road	16
M	Number of impervious Imp road layers	16
M	Thickness of roof	15
E	Mean wall emissivity	15
A	Mean wall albedo	15
A	Buildings albedo	15
S	Soil layer thickness	14
M	Wall layer thickness	14
M	Thickness of impervious road	14
M	Number of walls	14
F	Impervious fraction	14
S	Number of soil layer used in case of diffusion physics in the soil	13
F	Urban fraction (Building + Impervious Fraction)	13
E	Buildings emissivity	13
U	Height of forcing	12
U	Material roughness length above, for heat - roof	12
U	Material roughness length above, for heat - road	12
U	Reference height	12
S	Soil heat capacity	12
E	Impervious surface emissivity	12
U	Roughness length above canyon for heat	11
S	B parameter	11
S	Hydraulic conductivity at saturation	11
A	Impervious surface	11
T	Mean internal building temperature	10
U	Material roughness length above, for momentum - road	9

S	Saturation soil suction	9
F	Natural soil/veg fraction/pervious fraction	9
V	Vegetation wilting point	8
U	Effective roughness length above, for momentum - road	8
U	Material roughness length above, for momentum - wall	8
F	Grass fraction	8
V	Height of trees	7
V	Maximum soil moisture content (porosity)	7
V	Roughness length grass	7
U	Averaged building separation	7
T	Temperature for the soil	7
T	Temperature for the deep soil	7
S	Sand proportion	7
S	Clay proportion	7
E	Tree emissivity	7
E	Grass emissivity	7
V	VIS albedo	6
V	Height of grass	6
V	Ratio of surface roughness lengths	6
T	Surface temperature for road	6
S	Soil moisture content SMC	6
F	Tree fraction	6
A	Grass albedo	6
V	UV albedo	5
V	NIR albedo	5
V	Grass rooting depth	5
V	Tree rooting depth	5
V	Roughness length tree	5
V	Minimum stomatal resistance (MSR)	5
U	Average building width	5
U	Effective roughness length above, for heat - roof	5
T	Minimum interior building temperature	5
T	Surface temperature	5
S	Constant temperature of deep soil (1m)	5
S	Reference soil moisture (field capacity), mean of all layers	5
M	Emissivity of pervious road (top layer)	5
M	Volumetric heat capacity of pervious road layer 1	5
A	Tree albedo	5
A	Pervious surface albedo	5
V	Maximum vegetation-canopy water holding capacity tree	4
V	Maximum vegetation-canopy water holding capacity grass	4

V	Critical normalized soil water content for stress parameterisation	4
V	Maximum vegetation-canopy water holding capacity	4
U	Overall roughness length	4
U	Effective roughness length above, for momentum - wall	4
T	Deep road temperature	4
T	Surface temperature for roof	4
T	Surface temperature for wall	4
S	Loam proportion	4
S	Reference soil moisture top layer	4
M	Number of pervious road layers	4
M	Albedo of pervious road (top layer)	4
E	Pervious surface emissivity	4
V	Rooting depth	3
V	LAI of canyon vegetation	3
V	Air dry soil moist content limit	3
U	Floor density distribution of the buildings in vertical direction	3
U	Sub-layer Stanton number	3
U	Zero plane displacement height - roof	3
T	Maximum interior building temperature	3
M	Mean pervious road layer thickness	3
QF	Total anthropogenic heat	3
V	Heat capacity of grass	2
V	Heat capacity of trees	2
V	Heat capacity of vegetation	2
V	Parameters used in radiation stress function	2
V	Parameter used in vapour pressure deficit function	2
U	Wall surface : horizontal surface	2
U	Mean block length	2
U	Effective roughness length above, for heat - wall	2
U	Zero plane displacement height - road	2
U	Zero plane displacement height - wall	2
U	Effective roughness length above, for heat - road	2
S	Moisture availability - roof	2
S	Soil quartz content	2
M	Thermal conductivity of pervious road layer 1	2
QF	Sensible from traffic	2
V	Computation used to determine MSR	1
V	Optimum temperature in Temperature stress function	1
V	Mesophyll conductance	1
V	Coefficient for maximum interception water storage capacity	1
V	Ecosystem respiration parameter	1

V	Ratio d(biomass)/d(lai)	1
V	e-folding time for senescence	1
V	Cuticular conductance	1
V	Maximum air saturation deficit	1
V	Leaf area ratio sensitivity to nitrogen	1
V	Lethal minimum value of LA ratio	1
V	Nitrogen concentration of biomass	1
V	Vegetation thermal inertia coefficient	1
V	Root fraction layer 1	1
U	Mean long axis azimuth of walls	1
U	Sky view factor	1
U	Material roughness length above, for heat - wall	1
U	Slope data / Slope type	1
T	Temperature for the root zone	1
S	Sub-grid runoff coefficient	1
S	Moisture availability - wall	1
S	Moisture availability - road	1
S	Fraction irrigated - Impervious road	1
S	Fraction irrigated - Tree	1
S	Fraction irrigated - Grass	1
QF	Sensible from industry	1
QF	Thermal inertia	1
A	Building albedo range lower	1
A	Urban tile albedo	1

Action by 1 January 2009: for your model run(s), where relevant, we would like the parameter values for Table 2a. It may be that you do not specifically require these values but that they are intrinsic to the calculation of other variables and as such, can be derived from the relations presented in Table 2-d. This will allow more direct comparisons of parameter values.

Numerous parameter details have been circulated in graphical form. However, we would like to ensure that participants have confirmed the exact data that will be compared between models. As such, each group will be sent a spreadsheet with the values we have for each stage.

Action by 1 January 2009: please confirm the parameter details are correct and/or provide modifications where necessary.

VL92 Results

Results for the VL92 dataset, incorporating any reruns, are presented in the following figures. These are for an analysis between days 225 and 237 (i.e.

n=312 hours of observation), with the following time-period definitions:

- a) **Transition:** $[Q^*_{t,t+1} < 0 + Q^*_{t+2} >= 0]$
 $[Q^*_{t,t+1} < 0 + Q^*_{t+2} <= 0]$

else

- b) **Day** $Q^*_t > 0$
c) **Night** $Q^*_t < 0$
d) **All** all data

where the observed net all wave radiation, Q^* , is for a particular time, t .

Results for all models versus the observations are shown in Figure 1, and against time in Figure 2. Statistical results are shown in the next sequence of figures (Table 4). Where data are grouped, it relates to the model classifications (as confirmed by participants). The classifications consist of:

- 1) Vegetation inclusion (Table 5):
 - a) Integrated: vegetation is within the tile that has the build facets so can interact/respond to the exchanges associated with this layer of the model.
 - b) Separate Tile: the vegetation and built parts of the surface are treated separately and do not interact until a layer above the surface scheme. The fluxes are a spatially weighted mean.
 - c) None: assumed to be no vegetation present.
- 2) Urban land surface scheme layers resolved (Table 6):
 - a) Slab
 - b) Single layer
 - c) Multi-layer
- 3) Facets and aspects resolved (Table 7):
 - a) Whole – individual walls, roof, road are not resolved.
 - b) Roof, Walls and roads are resolved but without orientation – therefore there are not sunlit and shaded facets resolved.
 - c) Roof, Walls and roads are resolved with orientation – therefore during the daytime there maybe sunlit and shaded facets.
- 4) Anthropogenic heat flux (Table 8):
 - a) Internal Temperature: An internal temperature is prescribed which is used to calculate the other fluxes

- b) Prescribed: flux value is prescribed
- c) Modelled: all or components of the flux are modelled
- d) None: the flux is assumed to be 0 W m^{-2} or not to exist.

Table 4: Summary of figure numbers plotting overall, ranked results for VL92 data. (a) Ranked plots for mean, standard deviation (SD), root mean square error (RMSE) and coefficient of determination (R^2) statistics. Each Figure consist of (clockwise, from top left) Q^* , ΔQ_S , Q_{LE} and Q_H results. (b) Taylor Plots for each flux. Each Figure consists of (clockwise, from top left) all, night, transition and day time periods results.

		Vegetation inclusion (5)	Layers resolved (6)	Facets/ aspects resolved (7)	Anthropogenic heat-flux (8)	
<i>Time period</i>		<i>All (n=312), Night (n=112), Day (n=128), Transition (n=76)</i>				
Statistic	Mean	3,4,5,6	19,20,21,22	35,36,37,38	51,52,53,54	
	SD	7,8,9,10	23,24,25,26	39,40,41,42	55,56,57,58	
	RMSE	11,12,13,14	27,28,29,30	43,44,45,46	59,60,61,62	
	R²	15,16,17,18	31,32,33,34	47,48,49,50	63,64,65,66	
(b) Taylor Plots:						
		(Table)	Q^*	ΔQ_S	Q_H	Q_{LE}
Ungrouped –all values			67	68	69	70
Vegetation (5)			71	72	73	74
Layers resolved (6)			75	76	77	78
Facets & aspects resolved (7)			79	80	81	82
Anthropogenic heat flux (8)			83	84	85	86

Table 5: Models in each class: vegetation inclusion. A-C as labelled on Figures

Integrated (A)	26,32,41,43,46
As tile (B)	13,16,21,25,30,31,35,36,37,39,42,47,49,50
None (C)	11,12,14,17,22,28,33

Table 6: Urban land surface scheme layers resolved models in each class. A-C as labelled on Figures.

Slab (A)	13,21,30,33,37,41,46,49,50
Single (B)	11,22,25,26,28,32,36,39,43,47
Multilayer (C)	12,14,16,17,31,35,42

Table 7: Models in each class: facets and aspects resolved. A-C as labelled on Figures. * R,W,R - road, wall, roof

Whole (A)	22,33,37,41,49,50
R,W,R* with orientation (B)	11,12,14,16,17,26,28,35,36,42,47
R,W,R* without orientation (C)	13,21,25,30,31,32,39,43,46

Table 8: Models in each class: anthropogenic heat flux. A-D as labelled on Figures.

Internal (A)	12,14,25,35
Prescribed all (B)	16,17,22,26,31,32,41,43
Not modelled (C)	11, 13,21,28,30,33,37,39,46,49
Modelled (D)	36,42,47,50

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Figure 1: Scatter plots comparing observed and modelled fluxes (VL92).

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Figure 2: Hourly variation in fluxes (VL92).

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Figure 3: Ranked mean flux values for all hours, grouped by vegetation inclusion (Table 5) (VL92).

Figure 4: Ranked mean flux values for nighttime hours, grouped by vegetation inclusion (Table 5) (VL92).

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Figure 5: Ranked mean flux values for daytime hours, grouped by vegetation inclusion (Table 5) (VL92).

Figure 6: Ranked mean flux values for transition hours, grouped by vegetation inclusion (Table 5) (VL92).

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Figure 7: Ranked standard deviation values for all hours, grouped by vegetation inclusion (Table 5) (VL92).

Figure 8: Ranked standard deviation values for nighttime hours, grouped by vegetation inclusion (Table 5) (VL92).

Figure 9: Ranked standard deviation values for daytime hours, grouped by vegetation inclusion (Table 5) (VL92).

Figure 10: Ranked standard deviation values for transition hours, grouped by vegetation inclusion (Table 5) (VL92).

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FIGURE 1: Alpha Stage 1, RMSE, All data (312 hours), n = 312

Figure 11: Ranked RMSE values for all hours, grouped by vegetation inclusion (Table 5) (VL92).

FIGURE 2: Alpha Stage 1, RMSE, Night data (312 hours), n = 312

Figure 12: Ranked RMSE values for nighttime hours, grouped by vegetation inclusion (Table 5) (VL92).

FIGURE 3: Alpha Stage 1, RMSE, Day data (312 hours), n = 312

Figure 13: Ranked RMSE values for day time hours, grouped by vegetation inclusion (Table 5) (VL92).

FIGURE 4: Alpha Stage 1, RMSE, Transition data (312 hours), n = 312

Figure 14: Ranked RMSE values for transition hours, grouped by vegetation inclusion (Table 5) (VL92).

Figure 15: Ranked R^2 values for all hours, grouped by vegetation inclusion (Table 5) (VL92).

Figure 16: Ranked R^2 values for nighttime hours, grouped by vegetation inclusion (Table 5) (VL92).

Figure 17: Ranked R^2 values for daytime hours, grouped by vegetation inclusion (Table 5) (VL92).

Figure 18: Ranked R^2 values for transition hours, grouped by vegetation inclusion (Table 5) (VL92).

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Figure 19: Ranked mean flux values for all hours, grouped by layers-resolved (Table 6) (VL92).

Figure 20: Ranked mean flux values for nighttime hours, grouped by layers-resolved (Table 6) (VL92).

Figure 21: Ranked mean flux values for daytime hours, grouped by layers-resolved (Table 6) (VL92).

Figure 22: Ranked mean flux values for transition hours, grouped by layers-resolved (Table 6) (VL92).

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Figure 23: Ranked standard deviation in flux values for all hours, grouped by layers-resolved (Table 6) (VL92).

Figure 24: Ranked standard deviation in flux values for nighttime hours, grouped by layers-resolved (Table 6) (VL92).

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Figure 25: Ranked standard deviation in flux values for daytime hours, grouped by layers-resolved (Table 6) (VL92).

Figure 26: Ranked standard deviation in flux values for transition hours, grouped by layers-resolved (Table 6) (VL92).

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FIGURE 1: Alpha Stage 1, RMSE, All data (312 hours), n = 312

Figure 27: Ranked RMSE in flux values for all hours, grouped by layers-resolved (Table 6) (VL92).

FIGURE 2: Alpha Stage 1, RMSE, Night data (312 hours), n = 312

Figure 28: Ranked RMSE in flux values for nighttime hours, grouped by layers-resolved (Table 6) (VL92).

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FIGURE 3: Alpha Stage 1, RMSE, Day data (312 hours), n = 312

Figure 29: Ranked RMSE in flux values for daytime hours, grouped by layers-resolved (Table 6) (VL92).

FIGURE 4: Alpha Stage 1, RMSE, Transition data (312 hours), n = 312

Figure 30: Ranked RMSE in flux values for transition hours, grouped by layers-resolved (Table 6) (VL92).

Figure 31: Ranked R^2 in flux values for all hours, grouped by layers-resolved (Table 6) (VL92).

Figure 32: Ranked R^2 in flux values for nighttime hours, grouped by layers-resolved (Table 6) (VL92).

Figure 33: Ranked R^2 in flux values for daytime hours, grouped by layers-resolved (Table 6) (VL92).

Figure 34: Ranked R^2 in flux values for transition hours, grouped by layers-resolved (Table 6) (VL92).

Figure 35: Ranked mean flux values for all hours, grouped by facets and aspects resolved (Table 7) (VL92).

Figure 36: Ranked mean flux values for nighttime hours, grouped by facets and aspects resolved (Table 7) (VL92).

Figure 37: Ranked mean flux values for daytime hours, grouped by facets and aspects resolved (Table 7) (VL92).

Figure 38: Ranked Mean flux values for transition hours, grouped by facets and aspects resolved (Table 7) (VL92).

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Figure 39: Ranked standard deviation in flux values for all hours, grouped by facets and aspects resolved (Table 7) (VL92).

Figure 40: Ranked standard deviation in flux values for nighttime hours, grouped by facets and aspects resolved (Table 7) (VL92).

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Figure 41: Ranked standard deviation in flux values for daytime hours, grouped by facets and aspects resolved (Table 7) (VL92).

Figure 42: Ranked standard deviation in flux values for transition hours, grouped by facets and aspects resolved (Table 7) (VL92).

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FIGURE 1: VL92, RMSE, All data (312 hours), n = 312

Figure 43: Ranked RMSE in flux values for all hours, grouped by facets and aspects resolved (Table 7) (VL92).

FIGURE 2: VL92, RMSE, Night data (312 hours), n = 312

Figure 44: Ranked RMSE in flux values for nighttime hours, grouped by facets and aspects resolved (Table 7) (VL92).

FIGURE 3: VL92, RMSE, Day data (312 hours, n = 312)

Figure 45: Ranked RMSE in flux values for daytime hours, grouped by facets and aspects resolved (Table 7) (VL92).

FIGURE 4: VL92, RMSE, Transition data (312 hours, n = 78)

Figure 46: Ranked RMSE in flux values for transition hours, grouped by facets and aspects resolved (Table 7) (VL92).

Figure 47: Ranked R^2 in flux values for all hours, grouped by facets and aspects resolved (Table 7) (VL92).

Figure 48: Ranked R^2 in flux values for nighttime hours, grouped by facets and aspects resolved (Table 7) (VL92).

Figure 49: Ranked R^2 in flux values for daytime hours, grouped by facets and aspects resolved (Table 7) (VL92).

Figure 50: Ranked R^2 in flux values for transition hours, grouped by facets and aspects resolved (Table 7) (VL92).

Figure 51: Ranked mean of flux values for all hours, grouped anthropogenic heat-flux (Table 8) (VL92).

Figure 52: Ranked mean of flux values for nighttime hours, grouped anthropogenic heat-flux (Table 8) (VL92).

Figure 53: Ranked mean of flux values for daytime hours, grouped anthropogenic heat-flux (Table 8) (VL92).

Figure 54: Ranked mean of flux values for transition hours, grouped anthropogenic heat-flux (Table 8) (VL92).

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Figure 55: Ranked standard deviation of flux values for all hours, grouped anthropogenic heat-flux (Table 8) (VL92).

Figure 56: Ranked standard deviation of flux values for nighttime hours, grouped anthropogenic heat-flux (Table 8) (VL92).

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Figure 57: Ranked standard deviation of flux values for daytime hours, grouped anthropogenic heat-flux (Table 8) (VL92).

Figure 58: Ranked standard deviation of flux values for transition hours, grouped anthropogenic heat-flux (Table 8) (VL92).

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FIGURE 1: VL92, RMSE, All data (312 hours), n = 312

Figure 59: Ranked RMSE of flux values for all hours, grouped anthropogenic heat-flux (Table 8) (VL92).

FIGURE 2: Alpha Stage 1, RMSE, Night data (312 hours), n = 312

Figure 60: Ranked RMSE of flux values for nighttime hours, grouped anthropogenic heat-flux (Table 8) (VL92).

FIGURE 3: Alpha Stage 1, RMSE, Day data (312 hours), n = 312

Figure 61: Ranked RMSE of flux values for daytime hours, grouped anthropogenic heat-flux (Table 8) (VL92).

FIGURE 4: Alpha Stage 1, RMSE, Transition data (312 hours), n = 312

Figure 62: Ranked RMSE of flux values for transition hours, grouped anthropogenic heat-flux (Table 8) (VL92).

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Figure 63: Ranked R^2 of flux values for all hours, grouped anthropogenic heat-flux (Table 8) (VL92).

Figure 64: Ranked R^2 of flux values for nighttime hours, grouped anthropogenic heat-flux (Table 8) (VL92).

Figure 65: Ranked R² of flux values for daytime hours, grouped anthropogenic heat-flux (Table 8) (VL92).

Figure 66: Ranked R² of flux values for transition hours, grouped anthropogenic heat-flux (Table 8) (VL92).

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Figure 67: Taylor plots for Q^* fluxes. For Legend see Figure 1.

Figure 68: Taylor plots for ΔQ_s fluxes. For Legend see Figure 1.

Figure 69: Taylor plots for Q_H fluxes. For Legend see Figure 1.

Figure 70: Taylor plots for Q_E fluxes. For Legend see Figure 1.

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Figure 71: Taylor plots for Q^* fluxes, grouped by vegetation inclusion.

Figure 72: Taylor plots for ΔQ_s fluxes, grouped by vegetation inclusion. For Legend see Figure 71.

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Figure 73: Taylor plots for Q_H fluxes, grouped by vegetation inclusion. For Legend see Figure 71.

Figure 74: Taylor plots for Q_{LE} fluxes, grouped by vegetation inclusion. For Legend see Figure 71.

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Figure 75: Taylor plots for Q^* fluxes, grouped by layers resolved.

Figure 76: Taylor plots for ΔQ_s fluxes, grouped by layers resolved. For Legend see Figure 75.

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Figure 77: Taylor plots for Q_H fluxes, grouped by layers resolved. For Legend see Figure 75.

Figure 78: Taylor plots for Q_{LE} fluxes, grouped by layers resolved. For Legend see Figure 75.

Figure 79: Taylor plots for Q^* fluxes, grouped by facets and aspects resolved.

Figure 80: Taylor plots for ΔQ_s fluxes, grouped by facets and aspects resolved. For Legend see Figure 79.

Figure 81: Taylor plots for Q_H fluxes, grouped by facets and aspects resolved. For Legend see Figure 79.

Figure 82: Taylor plots for Q_{LE} fluxes, grouped by facets and aspects resolved. For Legend see Figure 79.

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Figure 83: Taylor plots for Q^* fluxes, grouped by anthropogenic heat-flux.

Figure 84: Taylor plots for ΔQ_s fluxes, grouped by anthropogenic heat-flux. For Legend see Figure 83.

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Figure 85: Taylor plots for Q_H fluxes, grouped by anthropogenic heat-flux. For Legend see Figure 83.

Figure 86: Taylor plots for Q_{LE} fluxes, grouped by anthropogenic heat-flux. For Legend see Figure 83.

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This project contributes to:

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